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D5.1 Guidelines for Openness and Diversity in Citizen Science

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Abstract	This deliverable presents evidence-based guidelines for promoting openness and diversity in citizen science, drawing on insights from seven inclusive pilot projects and ten public library events implemented across Europe between 2023 and 2025 within the ECS project. The pilots engaged underrepresented groups including older adults, migrants, fishing communities, hunters, youth from underserved backgrounds, people with disabilities, and young children. Through thematic analysis of pilot documentation, consultation notes, capacity building workshops, and impact stories, this work identifies key drivers of success and

persistent barriers to inclusive participation. Critical findings reveal that co-creation from project inception, provision of multiple participation pathways beyond digital technologies, building trust through sustained commitment, and valuing social connection alongside scientific contribution are essential for meaningful engagement. The guidelines are structured around four interconnected pillars: establishing a foundational mindset of intersectionality and community benefit, implementing genuine co-design and participatory approaches, ensuring accessible implementation and engagement, and committing to sustaining impact and relationships. This deliverable aims to support citizen science practitioners, libraries, policy makers, and funders in creating more inclusive and impactful initiatives that democratise who participates in and benefits from scientific knowledge creation.

Keywords

Citizen science, inclusivity, diversity, openness, co-creation, underrepresented groups, participatory research, public libraries, community engagement, equity, accessibility, intersectionality, community-based research, social inclusion

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
ECS	European Citizen Science
EDI	Equity, diversity and inclusion
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
PL2030	Public Libraries 2030
CB	Capacity building
CS	Citizen science
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
AI	Artificial Intelligence

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents evidence-based guidelines for promoting openness and diversity in citizen science, drawing on insights from inclusive pilot activities and citizen science events implemented across Europe within the ECS project between 2023 and 2025. Seven pilot projects engaged groups underrepresented in citizen science including older adults, migrants, fishing communities, hunters, youth from underserved backgrounds, people with disabilities, and young children. Simultaneously, ten public libraries across European countries organised citizen science events reaching diverse audiences, including communities traditionally distant from scientific activities. Three capacity building workshops provided complementary perspectives from the broader citizen science community.

The pilots revealed several critical insights. Co-creation (involving communities in defining research questions and methods from the outset) proved essential for meaningful engagement. Technology, while valuable, can create additional barriers to the participation of certain groups; the most successful approaches

provided multiple participation pathways combining digital and analogue methods. Building trust with underrepresented communities requires sustained commitment beyond typical project timelines. Participants valued social connection, validation of their knowledge, and tangible relevance to their lives as much as scientific contribution.

These guidelines are structured around a clear, actionable framework of four interconnected pillars: establishing a foundational mindset of intersectionality and community benefit, implementing genuine co-design and participatory approaches, ensuring accessible implementation and engagement, and committing to sustaining impact and relationships. This structure guides practitioners from the initial philosophical commitment through to creating lasting, equitable impact. Each guideline is grounded in concrete evidence from the pilots and accompanied by practical recommendations. The deliverable aims to support citizen science practitioners, libraries, policy makers, and funding agencies in creating more inclusive and impactful initiatives across Europe and beyond.

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The ECS team honours the memory of Michael Køie Poulsen, who served as pilot leader for Nordeco's work in Greenland during the early stages of this project. Michael was deeply committed to community based monitoring and the meaningful inclusion of hunters and fishers in natural resource management. His dedication to giving voice to Arctic small-scale resource users in natural resource management exemplifies the values at the heart of openness, diversity and inclusion in citizen science. Though he passed away during the project's second year, his vision and contributions continue to inspire us and inform our understanding of what genuine partnership in citizen science requires.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context and objectives

Despite citizen science's participatory ethos, many initiatives struggle to engage diverse populations. For instance, research confirms that most citizen science participants belong to highly educated, academically skilled adult populations (Cooper et al. 2021; Vasiliades et al. 2021). This reflects a tendency within projects to inadvertently reinforce existing inequalities in who participates in and benefits from scientific research. The ECS project addressed this challenge through Work Package 5, *Boosting inclusion and diversity for mainstreaming citizen science*, which prioritised widening participation as a cross-cutting objective. Task 5.1 organised capacity building sessions for the citizenscience.eu community, national ambassadors, and library staff, focusing on promoting inclusivity across geography, gender, ethnicity, disability, age, and socio-economic backgrounds. Task 5.2 applied these principles through pilot activities designed to engage specific underrepresented groups.

For the purposes of this document, we adopt the following working definitions. **Openness** refers to making citizen science accessible to all potential participants regardless of background, removing barriers to participation and ensuring transparency in how contributions are used. **Diversity** encompasses engaging participants from varied demographics, experiences, and knowledge systems, recognising that different communities bring unique perspectives and expertise. **Inclusiveness** refers to ensuring meaningful participation where all voices are heard, valued, and empowered to have genuine influence on research processes and outcomes. Furthermore, we consider that **success** in inclusive citizen science initiatives is to be measured not only by scientific outputs but also by other aspects, including the depth of community engagement, the degree to which participants feel valued and empowered, the sustainability of relationships beyond project timelines, and the benefits, that come to all participating communities alongside research goals. Finally, in the context of this deliverable, **underrepresented groups** refers to both those who are demographically underrepresented in citizen science (due to barriers related to age, ethnicity, disability, etc.) and those whose valuable knowledge and expertise are often excluded from scientific processes, regardless of their demographic characteristics. These guidelines address both dimensions of underrepresentation.

This deliverable synthesises learnings from these activities to provide actionable guidelines for inclusive citizen science practices. The intended audiences include citizen science practitioners and researchers, libraries and cultural institutions, policy makers and funding agencies, community organisations, and national citizen science networks.

1.2. Methodology

The present guidelines are informed by a synthesis of multiple data sources and collaborative learning processes. The core evidence comes from seven inclusive pilot projects implemented by ECS partners and Affiliated Entities, which engaged diverse groups underrepresented in citizen science: older adults and migrant communities in Spain, teenagers who face barriers to educational success in Germany, fishing communities in Croatia, hunters and fishers in Greenland, kindergarten children in Portugal, and deaf and hard-of-hearing adults in Greece. Each pilot developed detailed action plans, documented their implementation, and evaluated their outcomes.

This was complemented by activities within the Public Libraries 2030 (PL2030) network, where ten libraries across Europe organised events related to citizen science. These included insect monitoring in Poland, environmental projects in Slovenia, place names collection in Latvia, seed libraries in Austria, project showcases in Denmark, biodiversity monitoring in Finland, and lecture series in Portugal, Greece, and Romania.

The evidence base was further enriched by three capacity building (CB) workshops organised under Task 5.1, which ran in parallel to the pilot activities and provided complementary perspectives from the broader citizen science community. CB1 (April 2024) gathered citizen science experts at the ECSA Conference to map inclusive CS projects across Europe, collecting 31 project examples targeting groups underrepresented in CS and identifying common barriers and solutions. CB2 (September 2025) focused on exploring art-based evaluation methods in the context of citizen science. CB3 (September 2025) served a dual purpose as both a wrap-up activity for T5.2 and as a mutual learning workshop that brought together library representatives and pilot leaders to co-create solutions to common challenges. While these workshops were not directly connected to the specific pilots and library events, the insights they generated helped validate patterns emerging from the pilot activities and informed the development of these guidelines.

The process was supported by Vanessa Mignan, an external equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) expert who conducted one-on-one consultations with pilot leaders, providing tailored advice on engagement and methodologies; detailed notes from these sessions captured ongoing challenges and solutions. Furthermore, impact stories and direct statements from pilot leaders and library representatives, featured in [The impact of citizen science: 12 stories from across Europe](#) (Schürz, Schaefer & Kieslinger, 2024), were used to enrich the findings. A mutual learning workshop then brought together pilot leaders and library representatives to share experiences and co-create solutions to common challenges.

All collected materials, including pilot documentation, consultation notes, and impact stories, were analyzed thematically by the lead author. This analysis involved the identification of recurring themes, challenges, and success factors across different questions, with support from AI tools (primarily Claude Sonnet 4.5 and ChatGPT-5.1 for initial pattern identification and synthesis of large text volumes. This analysis was iteratively refined through team discussions to ensure a nuanced interpretation and representation of insights, resulting in the elaboration of these guidelines.

Throughout this process, Stickydot coordinated support for both public library representatives and pilot leads, providing an external perspective crucial for identifying progress, concerns, and critical questions as activities unfolded. This outside view helped recognise blind spots and surface challenges that might otherwise have remained unexamined, which is a valuable function when working toward more inclusive and diverse citizen science practices.

2. Overview of inclusive activities

2.1. ECS pilots on engaging diverse communities

The ECS pilots (see Annex I for details) demonstrated remarkable breadth in the communities successfully engaged. **Science for Change** worked with 40 older adults across three locations using the OdourCollect app to monitor odour pollution in Barcelona, as this is an increasing concern in certain neighbourhoods.

The project specifically targeted individuals over 60 who typically show low engagement with technological activities. Rather than requiring app proficiency, the team created alternative pathways including artistic workshops where participants created olfactory memory timelines and artworks related to collected odours. This approach recognised that technology comfort varies significantly even within age groups, with those 60-70 generally more adept than those over 80.

The **Museum für Naturkunde Berlin** organised BioBlitz events with 20 students aged 13 from an integrated secondary school known for serving children and teenagers who face barriers to educational success with migrant backgrounds, learning difficulties, and cognitive challenges. Working closely with teachers who understood student needs, the team used gamified activities and provided high adult-to-youth ratios for adequate support. Students successfully generated over 40 research-grade biodiversity observations for the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) database, though evaluation revealed mixed results regarding long-term motivation to engage with nature.

Ibercivis engaged migrants from Latin American communities in Zaragoza in climate change adaptation discussions, as this group is traditionally excluded from scientific discourse. Initial outreach to large NGOs proved challenging, with a breakthrough coming through Venezuelan co-workers who served as community leaders. The project also worked with rural elderly women, as well as with younger people and workers who are outside of academic contexts, finding different priorities regarding climate change adaptation within these demographics. Where younger participants focused on heat waves in small urban dwellings, rural communities expressed greater concern about flooding.

Blue World Institute has worked for over many years to engage fishing communities in tracking dolphins and sea turtles through the Marine Ranger app. This relationship reflects the long timeline often needed to transform historically tense dynamics between fishers and marine conservation organisations. The institute learned that fishers communicate differently in large groups, small groups, and one-on-one settings, leading them to strategically combine all three formats. They also recognised that not all fishers are motivated to participate in data collection initiatives, so they adjusted their engagement strategy to include other activities, such as underwater clean-ups, as an alternative to continue building a relationship with this community.

Nordeco's PISUNA programme in Greenland, which started in 2009 amid concerns over the misalignment between scientific advice, policy quotas for hunting, and the realities of the hunters themselves, represents a mature example of community-based monitoring of living resources. Hunter and fisher communities established Natural Resource Councils that meet quarterly to discuss observations about wildlife and environmental changes, generating over 500 management proposals that directly influence local quota-setting and policy. The programme's long history demonstrates that when communities are given a voice in genuine decision-making processes, they are more receptive to restrictive regulations than comparatively to when these are imposed from outside.

Universidade Lusófona engaged kindergarten children aged 4-6 in co-creating urban solutions related to river sustainability. This age group is often excluded from being active participants in these processes, potentially representing a missed opportunity in terms of early education for sustainability, civic awareness, and responsibility. The project demonstrated that even very young children can contribute meaningfully to scientific inquiry when methodologies are appropriately adapted.

Web2Learn, meanwhile, established pathways for deaf and hard-of-hearing adults in Greece to participate in citizen science, working through the Youth Committee of the Deaf and Hard of Hearing Association to build on existing trust and community connections.

2.2. Library events

Public libraries emerged as critical partners in democratising access to citizen science. Their role as trusted community institutions with physical presence in neighbourhoods, diverse audiences, and missions centred on public access to knowledge makes them ideal intermediaries. While some library events (see Annex II for details) specifically targeted underrepresented groups, others engaged more broadly with their visitors to build institutional capacity for citizen science and position libraries as accessible venues for scientific participation.

The Valmiera Library network in Latvia coordinated a number of activities, including place names collection across over 30 libraries, engaging both seniors through familiar storytelling traditions and teenagers through digital documentation. This project collected toponymic data for a national database while creating intergenerational collaboration. Seniors provided knowledge and stories using pen and paper, while teenagers handled digitisation, a division recognizing different strengths rather than forcing uniform participation.

The Municipal Public Library in Kudowa-Zdrój, Poland, developed a comprehensive insect monitoring project combining education, data collection, and community celebration. Working with Stołowe Mountains National Park, they organised a Citizen Science Day featuring multiple speakers, distributed research kits for public borrowing, and created a mobile app with a questionnaire. The project successfully integrated into the annual Science Festival, demonstrating how libraries can embed citizen science into existing community programming.

Helsinki's Viikki Library, Finland, organised nature walks and biodiversity monitoring activities designed for seniors. By keeping walks short (two hours), taking the time to demonstrate the iNaturalist app, and partnering with the Finnish Museum of Natural History for expertise, they created accessible entry points. Participants showed an interest in maintaining engagement, with many claiming that they would continue to use the iNaturalist app independently. The library also hosted events with popular nature journalists, recognizing that familiar personalities can draw audiences who might not otherwise engage.

Libraries in **Kranj and Ljubljana, Slovenia**, took complementary approaches. Kranj focused on ongoing environmental initiatives including seed libraries, pollinator gardens, and bird protection, while Ljubljana organised workshops where researchers presented different citizen science projects to teenagers. Both demonstrated the flexibility of libraries to adapt citizen science to local contexts and existing programmes.

The **Lisbon Libraries Network, Portugal**, established an ongoing lecture series featuring university professors on diverse scientific topics, demonstrating how libraries can serve as venues for scientific discourse accessible to different publics. But this initiative also highlighted a common difficulty in the field, having evolved from the originally planned citizen science events into a more traditional science communication approach. This experience highlights the need for dedicated resources and guidance to help community partners bridge the gap between science communication and participatory research.

Austria's Bibliothek im Zentrum in Vienna developed different complementary citizen science initiatives. Their year-round seed library allowed users to collect and exchange seeds while receiving monthly gardening tips. The library also worked on presenting citizen science apps to users and planned to build a community garden using the iNaturalist app for tracking biodiversity. The library's approach emphasised building activities around existing community interests.

Romania's **ASTRA County Library of Sibiu** organised "Citizen Science - A New European Concept in the Lighthouse Libraries" in July 2024, gathering 25 high school students aged 14-18. Featuring an ornithologist as keynote speaker, the event explored ornithology, ecosystems, and bird diversity across habitats. The library emphasised citizen science as a means of enhancing communication between scientists and community members passionate about research, highlighting how collaborative projects can support scientific integrity while applying research outputs in local contexts.

Denmark's **Aarhus Kommunes Biblioteker** invited ten different citizen science projects to present their work at the library, with some performing activities that library users could participate in directly. The library also hosted a science kit on water quality in lakes called "søer i fritiden" (lakes in leisure time). This approach positioned the library as a venue for showcasing the diversity of citizen science opportunities while providing hands-on participation options.

Greece's **Veria Central Public Library** implemented "Scientists for a Day," a virtual masterclass about cancer research with projects directed by scientists from CERN, targeting high school students. The initiative created networking opportunities and generated additional ideas that extended beyond the initial activity, demonstrating how libraries can facilitate connections between youth and cutting-edge scientific institutions.

2.3. Capacity building workshops

Running in parallel to the pilot activities and library events, three capacity building workshops provided opportunities for cross-project learning and brought complementary perspectives from the broader citizen science community. While not directly connected to the specific pilots and events described in sections 2.1 and 2.2, these workshops helped validate emerging patterns, surfaced common challenges across different contexts, and contributed additional insights that strengthened the guidelines development process.

Capacity building 1 (CB1): Boosting inclusion in citizen science research processes took place at the 2024 ECSA Conference and engaged citizen science experts in mapping 31 inclusive CS projects across Europe. Participants worked in groups to identify barriers and successful strategies across four demographic categories: age, disability, socioeconomic status, and ethnicity. Common barriers identified included limited resources and time, difficulty recruiting and motivating participants, complexity of tasks, and digital literacy challenges. Successful strategies emphasised flexibility, co-creation, use of community networks, multiple communication channels, instant feedback, and keeping materials simple.

Capacity building 2 (CB2): Evaluating citizen science with art-based methods explored alternative approaches for capturing impact in citizen science projects. Organised in collaboration with the [PULSE-ART](#) project in the event *Layers of values: Exploring Impact in Culture, Art and Education*, the session brought together practitioners and researchers working at the crossroads of culture, education and science with a special focus on inclusive impact assessment. The session invited reflection on outcomes that are difficult to quantify through traditional metrics but are central to inclusive work, such as self-confidence, civic engagement, or social belonging. Participants examined two creative evaluation methods in depth: zines and videogames. Zines were identified as offering unique opportunities to share diverse points of view in collaborative and creative ways, encouraging multiple forms of expression beyond traditional formats and moving past strictly academic formats and accommodating a wide range of perspectives and experiences. Videogames as evaluation tools were seen as providing opportunities to meet target groups in spaces where they feel comfortable. Participants highlighted their potential to encourage reflection outside of conventional restraints such as traditional gender norms. Both methods

exemplified arts-based approaches that can capture dimensions of participant experience that are out of reach for standardised surveys and metrics.

Capacity building 3 (CB3): Mutual learning event on openness and diversity in citizen science brought together representatives from the library events and inclusive pilots described in 2.2 and 2.1. During the session, participants identified common challenges across contexts, such as difficulties reaching target groups, managing time and resource constraints, and balancing different participant needs. They also collectively developed strategies for addressing these challenges, such as connecting with ongoing community activities, going to third-party organisations with access to target communities, and providing a healthy mix of digital and analogue participation options for target groups.

These workshops validated and enriched the findings from pilots and library events, informing the guidelines presented in Section 4.

3. Key findings

The following findings synthesise insights from the pilot activities, library events, and capacity building workshops. While the pilots and library events provided deep, context-specific learnings, the CB workshops offered broader perspectives from the European citizen science community that helped validate and enrich these findings. Together, these complementary sources of evidence informed the development of the guidelines in Section 4.

3.1. *What worked: drivers of success*

The most successful aspects among pilot activities shared several characteristics. Co-creation from project inception proved critical. Nordeco's PISUNA programme has been able to sustain long term engagement because it addressed hunter and fisher communities' existing frustration with being excluded from resource management decisions. The project's primary goal was empowering communities to influence policy, with data collection serving that end. Similarly, U Lusófona recognised the value of involving kindergarten teachers in the early stages of designing their work with children, recognizing their expertise in engaging young learners, and the impact it could bring to their pilot.

Leveraging existing relationships and trusted intermediaries can consistently facilitate access to underrepresented groups. Ibercivis's breakthrough with migrant communities came through co-workers who were community leaders themselves. Web2Learn accessed the deaf community through a Greek Sign Language interpreter with established connections. Latvian librarians used personal knowledge of community members developed through years of presence in small towns. Also in CB1, participants documented successful strategies including reaching out to community organisations, using snowball recruitment, and employing peers as ambassadors to engage hard-to-reach groups.

Another promising approach displayed by projects was to provide multiple pathways for participation rather than requiring uniform engagement. Croatia's Blue World Institute offered app-based reporting, phone calls, and interviews. Latvia allowed both pen-and-paper and digital data entry. Science for Change in Spain created artistic alternatives for those uncomfortable with technology. In Finland, the Viikki

Library nature walks used adaptive approaches by maintaining focus on meeting the people where they are. They were also kept short and required no personal equipment, as the library provided tablets and phones loaded with the necessary apps. CB1 participants echoed these insights, pointing out that inclusive initiatives often resort to diverse recruitment methods, multichannel communication, and keeping participation materials simple. This flexibility proved essential because even within supposedly homogenous groups, tremendous diversity exists in capabilities, interests, and preferences.

Participants consistently valued social connection, validation of their knowledge, and tangible relevance to their lives alongside scientific contribution, suggesting that these more intangible outcomes might be promising avenues to encourage broader participation and sustainable engagement in citizen science. Older adults in Spain emphasised that the most important benefit was being able to talk, be heard, and feel valued. The social aspect of citizen science emerged as a legitimate outcome in itself, not merely a means to scientific ends. Projects captured these intangible outcomes through evaluation methods such as storytelling or focus groups, while CB2 explored the use of art-based tools, such as zines and videogames, for impact evaluation in citizen science.

Projects demonstrated tangible relevance to participants' lived experiences and concerns. Greenlandic hunters and fishers engaged because the project gave them voice in decisions directly affecting their livelihoods. Migrants engaged with climate adaptation when discussions connected to their own experiences. These insights are echoed in CB1 outcomes as well, as participants documented that projects addressing locally relevant issues showed high levels of motivation and engagement. Collectively, these findings challenge the assumption that people will participate simply because a topic is scientifically important. Instead, personal and community relevance prove to be powerful motivators.

These findings inform the ten guidelines in section 4 below.

3.2. *What didn't work: barriers and challenges*

Despite successes, pilots encountered significant challenges that provide important lessons. Reaching certain target groups proved more difficult than anticipated. Defining broad categories like "migrants" or "elderly" proved to be insufficient; projects needed to narrow focus to specific intersections such as "low-income migrants from Latin America" or recognise that people aged 60-70 have very different technological comfort than those over 80. Historical tensions between target groups and scientific institutions created trust deficits that we predict would require years to overcome. Blue World Institute's decades-long presence in fishing communities reflects realistic timelines for transforming historically contentious relationships.

Technology frequently created barriers rather than enabling participation. Many older adults over 70 lacked smartphones or interest in learning how to navigate new apps. Fishers found mobile apps impractical in field conditions involving rough weather, gloves, and boat motion. Even when apps were well-designed, the expectation that everyone would adopt digital tools could serve to exclude certain groups. As one pilot leader noted, if someone enters a project and fails to use an app, they can leave with a reinforced negative relationship with technology, resulting in the opposite of the intended outcome.

Short project timelines fundamentally constrained inclusive work. Building trust, co-creating methodologies, implementing activities, and sustaining engagement require time that typical project cycles cannot accommodate. Some pilots reported that relationships were just forming as funding ended. Furthermore, among the 31 projects mapped in CB1, limited time was the most frequently cited barrier

alongside limited resources, affecting projects across all demographic groups. **The tension between academic funding cycles and community engagement needs represents a structural barrier requiring systemic solutions.**

Resource and capacity constraints limited what small teams could accomplish. Projects required substantial staff time for personalised support, relationship building, and adaptation, often amidst other competing responsibilities. The question of compensating community members for their expertise and time created ethical tensions, with budgets often lacking provisions for appropriate payment. One consultation revealed an NGO partner asking whether participants would be reimbursed, highlighting that reliance on volunteer labour raises equity concerns, particularly when engaging low-income communities. This also represents a major challenge for public libraries, who are already facing challenges regarding staff capacity and budget constraints.

Designing activities that balance accessibility with scientific rigor presented ongoing challenges. Berlin's BioBlitz succeeded in engaging students and generating research-grade data, but post-activity evaluation showed students didn't necessarily become more motivated to spend time in nature or participate in future activities. This suggests that making activities "fun" may be insufficient if the goal includes fostering lasting engagement - a point reinforced in the consultations with the external EDI expert, who encouraged a bigger focus on structuring activities in a way that promotes engagement and strengthens children's connection to Nature. Projects sometimes struggled with whether to prioritise immediate accessibility or deeper learning, scientific protocols or community preferences, standardisation or local adaptation.

Lack of conceptual clarity regarding citizen science also created unexpected obstacles. Library practitioners reported unfamiliarity with the concept of citizen science, as well as its impacts and use cases before their involvement in ECS. Some library representatives eventually pointed out that they realised through their work in the project that they had already been engaging in citizen science activities without being aware of it. This lack of conceptual clarity can also lead to partners reverting back to more familiar models of expert-led science communication, as exemplified by the lecture series promoted by the Lisbon library network. At the same time, when practitioners did emphasise explaining citizen science concepts to target communities at the outset, this approach hindered rather than helped engagement. Communities responded better when activities began with issues they cared about rather than abstract definitions of citizen science. This highlights a fundamental challenge: practitioners need sufficient understanding to design effective initiatives, but leading with conceptual explanations to participants often creates barriers.

3.3. *Critical insights*

Several cross-cutting insights emerged from analysing successes and challenges together. The default to digital technologies in citizen science often undermines inclusion goals. While apps and platforms offer advantages for researchers, they create barriers for many groups underrepresented in CS. The most inclusive approaches combined digital and analogue methods, allowing people to participate in ways matching their capabilities and preferences. This finding invites the field to intentionally select tools based on the target community's needs and access, rather than defaulting to technology-based tools.

Relationship building is not preliminary to citizen science but central to it. Viewing community engagement as a phase that happens before the "real" research begins misunderstands the nature of inclusive work. The relationship is the foundation enabling everything else. **This has profound**

implications for how projects are structured, funded, and evaluated. If trust-building is essential rather than optional, short-term projects become inappropriate and at times even detrimental for inclusive goals.

Success requires recognizing multiple forms of value beyond scientific outputs. Projects measured only by data quantity or publication numbers miss crucial outcomes including community capacity building, social cohesion, validation of local knowledge, policy influence, and personal empowerment. Older adults collecting place names felt their knowledge was valued and preserved. Fishers slowly developed stewardship when the results of their observations were shared back with them through two-way communication pathways. These process outcomes often matter more to communities than scientific results, and are promising avenues to explore in the pursuit of long-term engagement and stronger buy-in for developed solutions. Here, arts-based evaluation tools, such as the ones explored in CB2, may offer an interesting avenue to measure these impacts.

Power dynamics between institutions and communities shape all interactions whether acknowledged or not. Pretending equality exists without addressing structural inequities perpetuates exclusion. Blue World Institute recognised that fishers may choose not to collaborate with marine conservation organisations as they can advocate for the introduction of protected areas, which can disrupt their activities. Public libraries also often wrestle with institutional power dynamics, particularly when it comes to their lack of recognition as valued partners by research institutions. This imbalance can represent a barrier to the establishment of effective partnerships.

4. Guidelines for open and inclusive citizen science

The following guidelines distill patterns that emerged consistently across the pilots, library events, and capacity building activities, validated through collaborative reflection with practitioners and participants. They are intended for diverse audiences engaged in or supporting citizen science: practitioners designing new initiatives, researchers seeking to broaden participation, library and cultural institution staff exploring science engagement, policy makers and funders shaping support structures, and community organisations considering partnerships. While not all guidelines will apply equally to every context, they provide a flexible framework that can be adapted to different contexts around Europe and beyond.

4.1. Foundational mindset and approach

Guideline 1: Use intersectional approaches rather than broad demographic categories

Categories like "migrants," "elderly," or "youth" are too broad to guide effective engagement. People's experiences reflect multiple intersecting factors including age, socioeconomic status, education, language, location, and ability. Crucially, this means engagement should be motivated by relevance, not just representation. A project is unlikely to succeed if it targets a group simply for being underrepresented without ensuring the research question resonates with their immediate concerns. With this in mind, projects should define target groups more specifically based on shared experiences

or challenges rather than single characteristics. Ibercivis initially struggled with "migrants" until narrowing to a more actionable definition, "Spanish-speaking migrants from Latin America living in low-income neighborhoods concerned about climate change". Within "older adults," the 60-70 age group showed markedly different technological comfort than those over 80, requiring different approaches. Consider using frameworks like the Wheel of Privilege to understand multiple dimensions of marginalisation and avoid essentializing any group.

Guideline 2: Frame projects around community priorities, not solely scientific agendas

People participate when they perceive personal or community relevance. Projects designed solely around researchers' questions often fail to motivate participation from groups who don't see how research addresses their concerns. Greenlandic hunters and fishers engaged because the project gave them voice in quota decisions directly affecting their livelihoods. Older adults in odour mapping participated because odour pollution was a genuine neighbourhood concern. Start by understanding what communities care about before defining research questions. Co-create questions reflecting shared interests, frame projects in terms of community benefits alongside scientific outputs, and be honest about limitations. Connect global or abstract issues to local contexts and manifestations.

Guideline 3: Commit to long-term engagement beyond project cycles

Meaningful relationships with target communities cannot be built in short project cycles. Trust develops over time through consistent presence and follow-through. Blue World Institute's decades in fishing communities demonstrates realistic timelines for transforming historically tense relationships. Short pilot projects often ended just as relationships were forming. Plan for sustained engagement beyond individual project timelines by seeking multi-year funding rather than short-term grants. Build institutional commitments rather than relying on individual researchers. This can include formal partnerships with community-based organizations, charities, and other trusted intermediaries who have long-standing relationships. Return to communities repeatedly, not just for data collection. Maintain communication between active project phases and support community initiatives even when not directly related to research. Be present for community events beyond that which is necessitated by the project. Plan strategies collaboratively to leave resources and capacity with communities, and determine how relationships will continue when funding ends.

4.2. Project design and co-creation

Guideline 4: Involve communities from inception through co-design

Among the most persistent issues identified was that projects are often designed first, then communities invited to "participate" in predetermined activities. True inclusion requires community voice in defining what will be studied and how. More collaborative approaches yielded better outcomes and more sustainable engagement, as seen in Nordeco's collaborative PISUNA model, which has achieved over 15 years of sustainability. Begin with listening and relationship building, not proposal writing. Invite community members to co-define research questions before seeking funding. Be prepared to adjust

research agendas based on community priorities and give communities decision-making power in aspects like methodology choices or resource allocation. This level of co-creation cannot be retrofitted, but must be embedded from inception. Making this standard practice requires funders to value and allocate specific budgets for the relationship-building and co-design phases that precede traditional research activities.

Guideline 5: Leverage community expertise and compensate it fairly

Leveraging existing trusted relationships through community leaders and organisations can provide essential bridges to access specific target groups. This was demonstrated by the broad community reach across all public library events, or by Ibercivis's breakthrough through Venezuelan co-workers who were community leaders. Researchers bring scientific expertise, but community members and practitioners bring crucial knowledge about their context and needs. The Museum für Naturkunde's pilot success depended on teachers' knowledge, and Science for Change relied on staff at geriatric centres who understood residents' capabilities. This expertise, which includes local knowledge, lived experience, and community access, should be valued and compensated, not extracted for free. Projects should consider budgeting for community compensation, or directly including community actors, including public libraries, as partners in funding applications, or even including compensation for public libraries, or . Otherwise, providing other forms of value exchange like skills training, data access, and visible acknowledgement of contributions can serve as fair rewards.

4.3. Accessible implementation and engagement

Guideline 6: Provide multiple entry points and participation pathways

Target groups may face diverse barriers that require flexible participation options. A thorough understanding of our target audiences' needs and motivations is crucial to develop appropriate participation pathways. Croatia offered app-based reporting, phone calls, and interviews for observations. Latvia allowed pen-and-paper or digital data entry. Spain provided artistic alternatives to technology use. Offer both digital and analogue options, allow varying time commitments from one-time to sustained engagement, create different contribution types including observation, identification, storytelling, and artistic expression. Accommodate different physical abilities with indoor and outdoor options, accessible locations, and varying activity levels. Provide materials in multiple languages and formats, letting people self-select their level and type of participation rather than requiring uniform involvement.

Guideline 7: Address practical barriers proactively

Even motivated participants face practical obstacles. Mobility challenges affected older adults in geriatric residences. Language barriers excluded some migrant communities. Equipment costs prevent low-income participation. Ask target communities about barriers before designing projects. Provide necessary equipment, materials, and transportation. Schedule activities at times that work for target groups rather than researcher convenience, i.e. outside the typical work hours. Consider providing compensation for time, especially for those with financial constraints. Ensure physical accessibility of locations, address language barriers through translation or visual methods, and minimise bureaucratic requirements for participation.

Guideline 8: Prioritise accessibility over default technology

Challenge the assumption that digital technology is always necessary. Depending on the context, technology can create additional barriers. Older adults over 70 often lacked smartphones or interest in learning apps. Fishers found apps impractical in field conditions. Start with “the interesting bits” of the research, first getting participants engaged in the question and methodologies, before introducing any technology. Consider low-tech alternatives like observation notebooks, phone calls, and paper forms. When technology is needed, build in time for familiarisation, or even co-design the applications with those that will use them. Furthermore, ensure physical and communication accessibility. Conduct accessibility audits of all venues and field sites. Ensure wheelchair accessibility, choose locations on public transit routes, and adapt field activities for various mobility levels. Make visual materials accessible and address language barriers through professional translation and visual communication methods.

4.4. Sustaining impact and relationships

Guideline 9: Provide continuous feedback and demonstrate impact

Participants need to see that their contributions matter and lead somewhere. Lack of feedback erodes motivation and reinforces the sense that communities are being used for research. Croatian fishers became more engaged when researchers shared information about dolphins they had reported themselves. Communities expressed frustration when recommendations disappeared without response. Report back regularly on how data are being used and show concrete outcomes including publications, policy changes, or conservation actions. Close the feedback loop by explaining what happened to community input. When recommendations aren't implemented, explain why. Celebrate successes publicly and acknowledge community contributions. Provide accessible summaries of research findings, not just academic papers. Create visible products such as exhibitions, community reports, or websites. Share data back with communities in usable formats. Furthermore, consider using art-based evaluation methods, like collaborative zines or videogames, to capture and value intangible outcomes. These creative outputs provide a rich, nuanced understanding of a project's impact that is often deeply valued by the community itself.

Guideline 10: Develop multi-stakeholder partnerships

Inclusive citizen science requires collaboration across sectors. Libraries provided community access that researchers lacked, while benefiting from the expertise brought by these researchers and their institutions. NGOs and community leaders provided community connections and trust. Museums offered exhibition spaces and expertise. Government agencies provided policy pathways and funding. Build partnerships from project design, not just implementation. Recognise different stakeholders' strengths and constraints, (e.g. public libraries bring different assets to the table than research institutions, and vice versa). Create formal partnership agreements clarifying roles, responsibilities, and benefits. Invest in relationship building across sectors and facilitate multi-stakeholder dialogue bringing different sectors together. Share resources and infrastructure including platforms, spaces, and networks. Document partnership models and lessons learned for others to build upon.

5. Conclusions

The ECS inclusive pilots and library events demonstrate that **citizen science can successfully engage diverse communities when designed with inclusion as a core principle rather than an afterthought**. From Greenlandic hunters influencing wildlife management policy to Spanish older adults documenting olfactory memories, from Croatian fishers tracking marine life to Latvian teenagers and seniors preserving place names, these initiatives prove that meaningful participation is possible across ages, backgrounds, and contexts.

Yet these successes required departing from conventional citizen science practices. They demanded recognizing community priorities alongside scientific agendas, sharing power in decision-making, building trust over years rather than months, and providing multiple pathways for participation that didn't assume universal technological comfort. The most impactful initiatives treated **relationship-building not as preliminary work but as the foundation enabling everything else**.

The guidelines presented here distil these lessons into actionable recommendations grounded in concrete European experience. They demonstrate that inclusion is not simply about broadening participation in existing structures, but about fundamentally rethinking how citizen science is conceived, funded, and practiced. This requires acknowledging power dynamics between institutions and communities, valuing diverse forms of knowledge and expertise, and accepting that the **most robust science often emerges from collaborative processes that honour community wisdom alongside academic training**.

The path towards true openness and inclusion in citizen science requires **commitment across the entire ecosystem**. Researchers should consider adopting co-creation approaches, recognising the potential added complexity to research designs as a worthwhile trade-off. Libraries and cultural institutions must leverage their trusted community positions to broker new relationships. Funders must provide timescales and flexibility that enable genuine partnership rather than extractive engagement. And communities should be empowered as knowledge holders and co-creators, not merely data providers.

The impact of citizen science in Europe should be measured not only by the volume of data collected or publications produced, but also by the extent to which it democratises who participates in and benefits from scientific knowledge creation. These guidelines are, due to their nature and the nature of the work they aim to support, not to be seen as a final product but instead as a work-in-progress that can be continually updated and improved. They are offered as a tool to help the field scale up its efforts, moving beyond exceptional pilot projects towards making openness and inclusivity a fundamental standard.

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Annex I. Table of inclusive pilot activities

Pilot lead organisation	Target group(s)	Country	Core activity / focus
Science for Change	Elderly people (65+)	Spain	Odour pollution monitoring using OdourCollect app; co-creation workshops, sensorial walks, and collaborative exhibitions.
Museum für Naturkunde Berlin	Teenagers from underserved communities (migrant background, special needs, learning difficulties)	Germany	BioBlitz event using the iNaturalist app for biodiversity observation and a pen-and-paper "BioBlitz Bingo" for gamification.
Ibercivis	Migrants from Latin American communities; rural elderly women; non-academic youth/workers	Spain	Focus groups on climate change adaptation as part of the Adaptation Agora project.
Blue World Institute	Local fishing communities	Croatia	Reporting sightings of marine mammals and by-catches of dolphins using the Marine Ranger app; direct dialogue and feedback.
Nordeco	Hunters and fishers	Greenland	PISUNA programme: Community-based monitoring and management of living resources, resulting in management recommendations for the government.
Universidade Lusófona	Kindergarten children (aged 4-6)	Portugal	riverChild project: Using living labs, educational games, and collaborative mapping to involve children in the assessment and preservation of urban rivers.
Web2Learn	Deaf and hard-of-hearing adults	Greece	Developing DHH-friendly educational materials within CitSci4All and co-creating mini citizen science projects.

Annex II. Table of library activities

Library	Target group(s)	Country	Core activity / focus
Valmiera City Library	Seniors; teenagers	Latvia	Collecting toponymic data for national database
Municipal Public Library in Kudowa-Zdrój	General; local community	Poland	Citizen Science Day and CS project - "Our insects count on you!"
Helsinki Viikki Library	Seniors; local community	Finland	Nature walks and biodiversity monitoring
Kranj City Library	General; local community	Slovenia	Seed libraries; pollinator gardens; bird protection
Ljubljana City Library	Teenagers	Slovenia	Workshops where researchers presented CS projects to teenagers
Lisbon Libraries Network	General	Portugal	Lecture series featuring university professors and researchers on scientific topics
Bibliothek im Zentrum	General	Austria	Seed library; presenting CS apps; planning community garden; biodiversity monitoring
ASTRA County Library	General	Romania	Presentations and debates about citizen science; identification of CS projects
Aarhus Kommunes Biblioteker	General	Denmark	Event showcasing 10 CS projects; hands-on activities, including water quality science kit
Veria Central Public Library	Teenagers	Greece	Virtual masterclasses on CS and research topics